

Enhancing energy harvesting capabilities using lead-free, flexible piezoelectric poly (vinylidene fluoride) tapes

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lead-free piezoelectric
Homopolymer poly (vinylidene fluoride)
Phase transformation
Poling
Piezoelectric properties
Energy harvesting

ABSTRACT

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) has been widely investigated as an energy harvesting material not only for its piezoelectric properties but also for being flexible, lead-free piezoelectric properties, and processing versatility. To enhance its piezoelectric performance, in this study, an additive was blended with PVDF to facilitate the crystalline transformation from α -phase to β -phase. This study explores the influence of two manufacturing processes, extrusion (EX) and compression moulding (CM), and the influence of different stretching and polarisation conditions on the piezoelectric performance of PVDF tapes for their integration into a cantilever beam for energy harvesting applications. The heat stretching process for EX and CM tapes was conducted at distinct temperatures (80° and 120 °C) and stretching speeds (300 and 10 mm/min), leading to different stretch ratios (3.0 and 4.50) that effectively raised the β -phase. Structural changes in the crystalline phases were identified using X-ray diffraction and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. Following this, the dipoles were oriented in the direction of an applied electric field (400–500 kV/cm). The piezoelectric performance was characterized by d_{33} values, and peak-to-peak voltage, under sinusoidal tensile stress, was obtained using a universal tensile testing machine. A d_{33} value of 25–30 pC/N and a peak-to-peak voltage of 27–35 V were obtained. Additionally, the piezoelectric behaviour was observed by arranging the tapes in a cantilever made of fibreglass composite and subjecting it to vibrational excitation at the resonance frequency. Maximum values of output voltage of 12 V for each tape were obtained under cantilever fixture.

1. Introduction

In recent years, piezoelectric materials have become a central focus of scientific research due to their potential for efficient, sustainable, and versatile energy harvesting. These materials are capable of sensing surrounding energy from the environment (such as vibration, human motion, wind, and ocean wave movement) and converting it into useable electrical energy [1–4]. This electrical energy can then power devices without the need for an external power source.

The piezoelectric effect occurs when a material produces an electrical charge in response to applied mechanical stress, as discovered by Jacques and Pierre Curie [5]. This phenomenon is caused by the realignment of dipoles in its non-centrosymmetric crystalline structure. Traditional ceramic piezoelectric materials with a non-centrosymmetric structure, such as lead zirconate titanate (PZT), barium titanate (BTO), and potassium sodium niobate (KNN), exhibit excellent piezoelectric response even when the polarisation is required. Nevertheless, these

ceramic materials are brittle, their manufacturing processes are complex and costly, and some, like PZT, can be harmful to the environment due to their lead content.

In order to address these challenges, scientists have investigated sustainable piezoelectric polymers. Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) stands out as the most suitable option due to its high dielectric constant, chemical resistance, flexibility, thermal stability, and suitability for a wide range of manufacturing processes. In its semi-crystalline nature, PVDF can adopt four distinct crystalline conformations, including alpha (α -), beta (β -), and gamma (γ -) phases. Among these crystalline phases, β -phase stands out with superior electroactive properties, including enhanced piezoelectric and ferroelectric performance, due to its dipole moment [6]. In terms of manufacturing processes, the extrusion method offers a cost-effective approach to producing solvent-free PVDF piezoelectric materials, particularly when compared to the electrospinning fabric process [3]. The filament obtained through the extrusion process has a high α -phase content due to the molten state and rapid cooling as it

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymeresting.2025.108838>

Received 29 January 2025; Received in revised form 30 April 2025; Accepted 5 May 2025

Available online 6 May 2025

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Scheme 1. Development route for obtaining polymer-based piezoelectric films. a) Compressed-moulded films (CM) obtained by filament extrusion, pelletizing and hot-press; b) Extruded films (EX) developed by flat die extrusion; c) Subsequent drawing process of extruded and compressed-moulded films (under strain and temperature) and (D) polarisation of drawn films (CM and EX films) under electrical field and temperature.

passes through a water tank bath. To enhance the β -phase content, various post-extrusion treatments have been extensively investigated, including extrusion-rolling [7–9], hot-pressing or uni/biaxial hot stretching while the material is in the molten state [8–12]. In contrast, the electrospinning process eliminates the need for post-treatment due to the inherent molecular orientation induced by the applied voltage and solvent evaporation [3]. The post-extrusion treatment is indispensable for transforming the α -phase into β -phase, a conversion that is key to attaining the desired electroactive phase and piezoelectric performance for energy harvesting applications.

The efficiency of crystal phase transformation depends on parameters like stretching temperature, speed, and draw ratio. The β phase is formed at around 80 °C [8,13,14], while higher temperatures favour the α phase [8]. Stretching speed has a smaller impact on β phase proportion compared to temperature. The draw ratio plays a crucial role in α -to- β phase transformation, optimal orientation being achieved at draw ratios up to 3 [15–17], combined with the temperature [13,14]. However, these methods alone are not enough to achieve the desired piezoelectric performance, as the dipoles need to be oriented.

After the α to β phase transformation, the dipole moments of the material are randomly orientated, resulting in a low piezoelectric coefficient, approximately 1 pC/N [7]. Therefore, to enhance the piezoelectricity, a polarisation process is required. The polarisation process allows the alignment of the dipole moments with the direction of the applied electrical field applied [8,18] creating a net polarisation and piezoelectricity. Basically, the polarisation can be performed either on-line or off-line by applying an electric field without contact [1], direct contact [19] and through corona discharge [14,18]. Each method has its specific requirements; for instance, contact poling needs sample preparation, including the electrodes deposition using conductive ink (silver or copper-based) [20]. Conversely, corona discharge involves a more complex setup. It is worth mentioning that the temperature, time, and electrical voltage are parameters to be optimized for a good piezoelectric property [7,14,19,21].

Herein, in this study, the enhancement of the β -phase of PVDF and polarisation conditions are investigated by using different methods for developing PVDF tapes: flat die extrusion and compression moulding followed by a drawing process. The method that yielded the most

Scheme 2. Scheme of non-poled material (left), alignment of dipoles with the electrical field during polarisation (middle) and poled material (right).

promising piezoelectric coefficient and output voltage for the PVDF was upscaled to produce PVDF tapes, which were incorporated into a cantilever beam, demonstrating its capability to generate electricity upon mechanical vibrations while proving its reliability for Energy Harvesting applications.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF homopolymer, Kynar 720) pellets were purchased from Arkema and dried at 100 °C for 1 day before use. BYK-MAX D 4221 is a copolymer containing functional groups typically used as a dispersing additive for siliceous fillers or pigments in thermoplastic. Its chemical interaction occur with both polar and non-polar structures, suggesting good compatibility across different polymer matrices. However, in this study, it was employed to enhance processing performance. BYK-MAX D 4221, in powder form, was obtained from TER® Group. Silver conductive paint was purchased from RS Components, and silicon oil (for polarisation in an oil bath) was acquired from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2. Methods

Scheme 1 illustrates the entire process of producing lead-free piezoelectric tapes.

The **Compression moulding process** (**Scheme 1a**, **Method A**) utilized a double screw extruder (HAAKE PolyLab QC) equipped with one feeding point, three heating zones along the barrel and a final heating die was used for the filament extrusion/compounding of PVDF-BYK 1 wt %. The extruder has a counter rotating conical twin-screw with intermeshing screws and a die head section of 2 mm. Barrel dimensions (290 × 750 × 210 mm). Extrusion temperatures of 160, 180, 200, 190 °C (T1, T2, T3, Td), screw speed of 30 rpm. The extruded filaments were pelletised and compressed moulded between stainless steel plates into the form of films in a hot press (Press Fontijne LabPro1000). The cycle used in the hot press consisted of 1) a heating ramp from room temperature to 190 °C (melting temperature) at 10 °C/min; 2) heating at 190 °C during 10 min (no pressure applied) and under 50 bar during 20 min; 3) cooling down to room temperature under 50 bar and at 5 °C/min. The obtained films were cut into films of smaller sizes (40 × 20 × 1.5 mm length x width x thickness) to be then drawn mechanically. The **Flat die extrusion manufacturing** (**Scheme 1b**, **Method B**) involved mixing PVDF homopolymer with 1 wt% of BYK during the extrusion. The compounded PVDF/BYK tapes was prepared in a twin-screw extruder (Rondol Technology Ltd., a length-to-diameter (L/D) ratio of 25) with five heated zones, including a die (38 mm flat width and 0.7 mm thickness). After being extruded, the flat film was cooled in a water bath (room temperature) and was pulled at 1.5 rpm. Extrusion temperatures of 205 °C, 210 °C, 210 °C, 205 °C, 205 °C (T1, T2, T3, T4 and Td), screw speed of 290 rpm. The **Drawing process** (**Scheme 1c**) comprises the

stretching process of extruded and compressed-moulded films was performed to induce the formation of β -phase spherulites and improve piezoelectric properties. The polymer chain orientation was strain-induced at a universal tensile testing machine under temperature. The extruded PVDF films were stretched at 80 °C at 300 mm/min, 300 % elongation (Shimadzu AGX-V 50 kN coupled to a thermostatic chamber model TCE-N300 with a thermocouple k-type) while the compressed moulded films were uniaxially drawn at 120 °C at a drawing rate of 10 mm/min, elongation of 450 % (Tensile testing machine MTS 250 kN, N°31030; temperature chamber MTS 651.06B-03 with a thermocouple k-type). After stretching, samples were quenched in water at room temperature to avoid the relaxation of the polymer chains. Dimensions (in length x width x thickness) of stretched extruded samples are 190 × 11.70 × 0.25 mm, and for extruded compressed-moulded are 180 × 10 × 0.45 mm. For the extruded films could be successfully stretched at 80 °C with a stretch ratio of 3, whereas the compressed-moulded films did not withstand these conditions and broke. However, they were successfully stretched at 120 °C with a stretch ratio of 4.5. For the **polarisation** (**Scheme 1d**), Silver ink was deposited onto both sides of both stretched types of films (top and bottom electrodes) and dried using heated air for approximately 10 min at 150 °C for the EX samples, while for the CM samples, the ink was dried at room temperature overnight. Silver electrodes were connected via crocodile clips to a DC power supply (Glassman high voltage, inc. 30 kV) for film polarisation. The poling conditions consisted of applying an electric field of 400–500 kV/cm to the films immersed in silicon oil for 30 min at a temperature of 80 °C. Throughout time, the temperature was decreased to freeze the dipole alignment (**Scheme 2**).

Afterwards, the cantilever was manufactured: the poled piezoelectric tapes were arranged, aligned, and bonded to a fiberglass composite (FGC) beam (FR4 glass fabric-based laminated, provided by Master-Platex, with a dimension of 23 × 4 cm) by using epoxy resin as an adhesive cured in an oven at 50 °C. The attached tapes to the cantilever were pressed down by using rubber and a steel block on top. Prior to the curing process, the series interdigit copper electrode pattern (bottom electrode) of the cantilever was connected to the tapes of the top electrode by soldering wires with tin to make the electrical connections.

2.3. Characterisation techniques

2.3.1. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The crystalline structure of PVDF was analysed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) (PerkinElmer Spectrum 100) coupled with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) using a diamond crystal. 8 scans run at wavenumber ranging from 1500 to 650 cm^{-1} using a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

2.3.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) characterisation (Bruker AXS D8 Discover, copper radiation ($\text{Cu K}\alpha_1$)) operated at 40 kV and 40 mA) was performed to further determine the crystalline phases of PVDF and crystallinity

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of PVDF samples, both stretched and non-stretched: a) extruded PVDF; b) extruded PVDF with 1 % BYK additive; c) compression moulding PVDF; d) compression moulding PVDF with 1 % BYK additive.

(angle rate from 10 to 40°, scanning rate of 0.04°/s [22]. The diffractograms were analysed using the Fityk software, with deconvolution performed using the Gaussian method.

2.3.3. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) (TA Instruments Q1000 modulated calorimeter) analyses were investigated. The specimens were heated from 70 to 200 °C at the heating/cooling rates of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere (50 mL/min).

2.3.4. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed in all samples to ensure the presence of dispersing agent after extrusion. Samples were heated from room temperature to 700 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere (constant flux of 50 mL/min).

2.3.5. Mechanical test

Tensile properties of extruded and compressed films after the drawing process were characterized by following the Normative UNE-EN ISO 527-3 (Plastics-Determination of tensile properties). A uniaxial strain gauge (general purpose foil strain gauges, KFGS-5-120-C1-11, from Kyowa) was bonded to the surface of the film with an adhesive (Loctite) (after cleaning the surface bonding site, polishing gently with sand cloth and cleaning again with ethanol) to measure the strain and determine the associated stress. The electrical resistance measured by the strain gauge was recorded with a data acquisition system HBM QuantumX MX1615B/MX1616B (strain gauge amplifier module). Uniaxial strain gauge connected to the acquisition system with 2 wires, in quarter bridge configuration, DC.

2.3.6. Piezoelectric performance

To determine the piezoelectric properties, d33 piezoelectric coefficient values were measured (d33 m YE2730, Sinocera) in several points along the samples. This measurement was carried out 48 h after polarisation to prevent the accumulation of electrostatic charges. An average of 7 values were considered. The piezoelectric performance/output voltage response (peak-to-peak, V_{p-p}) was measured upon tensile tests (Universal tensile test machine Shimadzu AGX-V, load cell of 5 kN). A standard tensile grip for the 5 kN load cell [23] was used. Output voltage recorded by an oscilloscope (Tektronix MDO305, probe 10x, 10 MΩ of internal resistance) under the application of mechanical force (40 N) and mechanical release (down to 0 N) at a speed rate of 300 mm/min (1 cycle) and repeated up to 10 cycles. 8 samples were tested to ensure reproducible results.

2.3.7. Cantilever beam

The cantilever's piezoelectric output performance in d33 mode was evaluated by vibrating excitation source generated at 12 Hz and amplified by an EAC-S 250 V300 single phase AC source by ETPS. A support was positioned at the center of the vibrating shaker to secure one end of the cantilever, allowing the other end to oscillate freely. The resulting output voltage was recorded by an oscilloscope (Tektronix MDO305, probe 10x, 10 MΩ of internal resistance).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. β -phase content by fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR analyses were carried out to verify the content and improvement of β -phase by the drawing process. The FTIR spectrum of

Table 1
FTIR bands of the electroactive phase of PVDF (Adapted from Ref. [26]).

Band position (cm ⁻¹)	Phase
1275	β
1431	β
840	β + γ
811	γ
1234	γ
881	α + β + γ
1070	α + β + γ
1176	α + β + γ
1401	α + β + γ

Table 2
Absorbance peaks data obtained by FTIR and analyses of β-phase content of extruded and compressed moulded samples before and after stretching.

Sample reference	β-phase (%)
EX PVDF non-stretched	*
EX PVDF stretched	32.3 ± 1.1
EX PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched	32.8 ± 1.88
EX PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched	32.5 ± 0.1
CM PVDF non-stretched	82.0 ± 1.0
CM PVDF stretched	37.9 ± 3.7
CM PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched	57.3 ± 10.1
CM PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched	33.2 ± 1.0
	49.9 ± 2.8

compressed moulded and extruded samples is presented in Fig. 1. The α-phase showed absorption bands at 762, 796, 974, 1145, 1211, and 1382 cm⁻¹ common to all samples [24]. The post-stretched samples showed vibrational bands at 1432, 1275 and 840 cm⁻¹, indicating a higher β-phase content; nevertheless, while the 1432 and 1275 cm⁻¹ bands are unique to the β-phase, the 840 cm⁻¹ band overlapped to the γ-phase at 811 cm⁻¹ [25,26]. The band at 1234 cm⁻¹, assigned to the γ-phase, exhibited weak absorption in the stretched samples. In the non-stretched sample, it is challenging to identify, as it appears to be overlapped. Table 1 presents the electroactive phases along with the vibrational bands common to the α, β, and γ crystalline phases. These

vibrational bands at 1401 and 1070 cm⁻¹ are presented in all the samples, although the vibrational band at 881 cm⁻¹, related to α, β and γ-phase, shifted to the band at 872 cm⁻¹. Additionally, after the post-stretching treatment, the band at 1178 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1162 cm⁻¹ and 1172 cm⁻¹ for the EX- and CM PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched samples, respectively. The lack of this shifting in the EX- and CM PVDF, both stretched and non-stretched, may be due to the presence of BYK, which positively contributes to chain orientation.

To calculate the relative amount of β-phase, the following equation was used [27]:

$$F(\beta) = X_{\beta}/X_{\alpha} + X_{\beta} = A_{\beta} / \left(\frac{K_{841}}{K_{764}} \right) A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta} = A_{\beta} / 1.26 A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta} \quad (1)$$

in which X_{β} and X_{α} are the crystalline mass fractions of α- and β-phase and A_{α} and A_{β} correspond to the absorbance intensities at 764 and 840 cm⁻¹ respectively. The K_{841} (7.7×10^4 cm²/mol) and K_{764} (6.1×10^4 cm²/mol) parameters are the absorption coefficients at the respective wavenumbers [23,28].

The flat-die extrusion process led to an increased β-phase content, highlighting the positive impact of aligning PVDF chains during stretching. This alignment enables the material to endure extended strains at high stretching speeds of 300 mm/min at a temperature of 80 °C. In contrast, the samples obtained through compression moulding showed a lower content of β-phase, which could be related to the lower stretched ratio (below 5) applied at higher temperatures (above 100 °C), resulting in an insufficient reorganization of polymer chains into β orientation mainly due to the low stretching speed (10 mm/min) a high temperature (120 °C) [14,16]. These results demonstrate that the key role of the drawing is the temperature that the β-phase is converted [8], also observed by Li et al. [16] who noticed a reduction of the β phase at high temperatures, specifically above 100 °C. The results are presented in Table 2.

Moreover, it must be pointed out that the addition of 1 % BYK slightly enhanced the β-phase compared to neat PVDF stretched, this is most noticeable in the EX procedure. The chemical composition of BYK suggests the presence of polar functional groups and a low melting temperature, which may facilitate chemical interactions with the PVDF

Fig. 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of PVDF and PVDF/BYK films obtained by extrusion a-b) and compression c-d) methods before and after the stretching process.

Table 3

Crystallinity values obtained by XRD and DSC for extruded and compressed moulded samples.

Sample reference	%Xc (XRD)	%Xc (DSC)	% β -phase (FTIR)
PVDF pellet (Kynar 720)	^a	33.5 \pm 1.8	^a
EX PVDF non-stretched	47.7 \pm 2.2	38.9 \pm 3.1	32.3 \pm 1.1
EX PVDF stretched	65.6 \pm 3.3	42.6 \pm 3.8	32.8 \pm 1.88
EX PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched	48.2 \pm 5.4	51.8 \pm 3.4	32.5 \pm 0.1
EX PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched	58.2 \pm 5.8	44.2 \pm 2.8	82.0 \pm 1.0
CM PVDF non-stretched	58.8 \pm 3	52.6 \pm 0.27	37.9 \pm 3.7
CM PVDF stretched	60.2 \pm 5.1	57.5 \pm 1.2	57.3 \pm 10.1
CM PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched	57.4 \pm 1.7	54.0 \pm 2.8	33.2 \pm 1.0
CM PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched	53.1 \pm 5.5	57.6 \pm 0.34	49.9 \pm 2.8

^a n/a – XRD analysis was not performed on the PVDF pellet due to its irregular shape and the limitations of the sample holder.

chain, thereby promoting crystallization [29,30].

The extruded and stretched PVDF-BYK 1 % exhibited an 82 % β -phase, while compressed-moulded and stretched films displayed a maximum β -phase content of 50.4 %. This variation could be related to the different drawing parameters applied to compression-moulded films, which do not withstand low drawing temperatures, resulting in only a low content of α -phase (15.2 %) being transformed into β -phase through the stretching process.

3.2. Crystallinity degree by X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Fig. 2 Shows the X-ray diffraction pattern of the PVDF and PVDF-BYK 1 % films. The crystalline phases of PVDF (α , β , and γ phases) are differentiated by their characteristic peak positions (2θ), altered intensities, and the incidence of new peaks, while certain crystalline phases might display identical diffraction patterns. The peaks observed at 17.3° (100), 18.3° (020), 19.7° (110), and 26.3° (021) predominantly correspond to α -phase, as exhibited in Fig. 2, for the non-stretched PVDF prepared using both approaches. In good agreement with the FTIR results, thermal-strain orientation induced at the Universal tensile test changed the PVDF chain conformation from α -phase to β and γ -phase. Therefore, the diffractogram exhibited an intense and well-defined peak at $2\theta = 20.5^\circ$ correlated to β -phase due to the combined contributions of the two lattice planes, (110) and (200), as well as the peak at 36.2° (022) and (310) appeared [31,32].

The peak at 20.5°, corresponding to the β -phase, is observed in all specimens tested, consistent with FTIR results. Compression-moulded samples exhibit a pronounced shoulder at 17.74 and 18.6°, indicative of the α -phase, which accounts for the reduced proportion of β -phase detected in FTIR analysis [6]. These peaks are less pronounced in the stretched EX PVDF samples, regardless of whether they contain 1 % BYK, indicating an effective transformation of the α -phase into the β -phase.

The degree of crystallinity (X_c) was calculated by the method of curve deconvolution considering the integrated areas of the deconvoluted peaks by using the Gaussian function type [33]. In this approach, the amorphous halo was centred around 18–19°, and additional peaks were manually introduced to ensure an accurate fit [26].

The equation applied was:

$$X_c = \frac{\sum A_c}{\sum A_c + A_a} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where A_c represents the area of the peak matching the crystalline phases, and A_a indicates the area corresponding to the amorphous phase. As observed in Table 3, interestingly, the degree of crystallinity increased by 37.5 % for EX-PVDF stretched samples when compared to non-stretched samples. Similarly, stretched EX PVDF-BYK 1 % samples exhibited a 20 % increase in crystallinity degree compared to samples

Fig. 3. a) First heating and b) cooling DSC curves of PVDF pellets and PVDF, as well as PVDF/BYK samples, analysed before and after stretching during flat extrusion processing; c) and d) Corresponding DSC curves for samples prepared via compression moulding.

Table 4

Melting and crystallization temperatures and associated enthalpies were obtained from the first heating and cooling DSC thermograms.

Samples reference	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	T_c (°C)	ΔH_c (J/g)
PVDF Kynar 720	175.8	33.5	133.4	48.6
EX PVDF non-stretched	169.8	39.4	137.7	54.3
EX PVDF stretched	166.1	41.0	138.5	54.6
EX PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched	168.6	54.1	140.5	
EX PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched	165.0	40.7	138.6	54.0
CM PVDF non-stretched	165.9	55.7	137.5	46.8
CM PVDF stretched	169.1	59.9	138.0	55.8
CM PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched	170.5	57.2	138.3	47.6
CM PVDF-BYK 1 % stretched	168.8	60.8	139.7	56.4

Fig. 4. TGA curves of PVDF-BYK 1 % a) Extruded (EX) and b) compressed-moulded samples (CM) vs BYK and neat PVDF. TGA tests under N_2 .

not subjected to the drawing process. Conversely, the enhancement of crystallinity for compressed-moulded samples is meaningless showing an increase of 2.85 % for CM PVDF and 0.93 % for CM PVDF-BYK 1 % both stretched samples in comparison with non-stretched. The minor variation noted in the compression-moulded samples aligns with observations made by Gomes et al. [13], who noted that at temperatures above 120 °C, the crystal lattice struggles to conform to the β -phase due to elevated chain mobility that tends to orient the crystal along the stretching direction. This phenomenon elucidates why the crystallinity

Fig. 5. a) CM PVDF sample before and after breaking point during strain test performed in Shimadzu universal testing machine; b) Samples dimensions adapted from UNE-EN ISO 527-3:2019.

degree is comparably uniform, as is the β -phase content discerned from FTIR analysis [7].

3.3. Thermal behaviour and crystallinity degree by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests were conducted to investigate the thermal behaviour associated with the two manufacturing processes and phase transformations of PVDF and PVDF/BYK samples through uniaxial stretching. The thermal properties of the samples were analysed and compared to those of the PVDF pellet as a control.

All of the samples, regardless of whether they were stretched or not, demonstrated a shift in the melting peak towards lower temperatures in comparison to the PVDF pellet, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Szweczyk et al. [34] noted that the PVDF pellet has a high melting temperature (T_m) due to its significant α -phase content. When the filament is extruded and rapidly cooled in water, the crystalline structure of the PVDF α -phase is altered, resulting in a decrease in T_m , as shown in Table 3.

While the β -phase cannot be distinguished from the α -phase using DSC, some researchers have reported that the melting point for stretched samples occurs at a lower temperature range of 160–167 °C [31,35]. Furthermore, a decrease in T_m is observed alongside an increase in the β -phase content in both CM PVDF and EX PVDF stretched samples, regardless of the presence of BYK. This reduction is attributed to the disintegration of crystal lamellae due to stretching, which reduces lamellar thickness [31,36]. This behaviour is accompanied by an increase in melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) values, indicative of the strong interactions between parallel dipoles in this configuration [34], as documented in Table 4.

The analysis of melting temperature (T_m) values for non-stretched CM PVDF indicated that the inclusion of 1 % BYK led to an increase in T_m from 165.8 °C to 170 °C, suggesting structural modifications within the crystalline framework. These changes are possibly due to the dispersing agent's ability to lower the nucleation's free energy barrier, thereby improving crystal perfection. Additionally, the compression moulding process, especially with the application of an 800 kN external force, was notably conducive to crystallization [10]. This effect is further augmented by the exposure of samples to a high temperature of 190 °C for approximately 30 min (encompassing both the heating and moulding steps), followed by methodical cooling at a rate of 10 °C/min to 25 °C. This precise temperature management facilitates the orderly arrangement of PVDF chains into a more defined crystal structure,

Table 5
Mechanical properties of Extruded (EX) and compressed-moulded (CM) for PVDF and PVDF-BYK.

Sample		Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Tensile Strength (Mpa)	Young's modulus (Gpa)	Max. Force (N)	Strain at break (%)
CM	Mean	0,47	10,31	229,32	2,66	1091,40	40,26
PVDF	Std. Deviation	0,07	0,65	17,51	0,65	77,48	8,82
CM	Mean	0,48	10,35	221,02	2,20	1081,60	32,40
PVDF-BYK	Std. Deviation	0,03	0,72	22,20	0,53	55,98	8,04
EX	Mean	0,27	11,68	188,96	2,69	594,80	26,42
PVDF	Std. Deviation	0,05	2,21	16,54	0,70	128,96	4,03
EX	Mean	0,23	11,9	230,38	3,31	641,6	27,86
PVDF-BYK	Std. Deviation	0,03	0,95	18,89	0,53	105,28	2,71

Fig. 6. Stress vs strain graphs of a) stretched and Extruded (EX) and b) compressed-moulded (CM) for PVDF and PVDF-BYK samples.

Fig. 7. d33 piezoelectric coefficient measurement for a) EX and b) CM PVDF-BYK 1 % to 7 replicates.

thereby contributing to the increase in melting enthalpy observed.

Although BYK can influence the crystallization of CM PVDF-BYK 1 % non-stretched, it did not function as a nucleating agent, as the crystallization temperature (T_c) remained quite similar across all samples [29].

DSC also gives information of the percentage of crystallinity of the samples which can be calculated by following the equation:

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H^0} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy of the polymer measured by DSC and ΔH^0 is the melting enthalpy of 100 % crystallization of PVDF (104.6 J/g) [30].

The degree of crystallinity calculated by DSC and XRD is summarized in Table 3. According to the DSC results, the stretched EX and CM PVDF samples exhibit higher crystallinity compared to their non-stretched

counterparts, suggesting the formation of more well-ordered regions. However, this trend is not observed in the samples containing 1 wt% of BYK. The EX-samples show a reduction in crystallinity, while the CM samples display only a slight difference, which can be attributed to the manufacturing process [28]. The differences in crystallinity values obtained from DSC and XRD can be explained by the distinct measurement principles of these techniques. DSC determines the mass crystallinity fraction (X_m) by analysing the enthalpy of fusion, which accounts for all crystalline regions, including small or defect-rich crystals. In contrast, XRD measures the volume crystallinity fraction (X_v), focusing more on well-ordered crystalline domains, as its intensity is influenced by the structural coherence and long-range order of the material.

By analysing the associated errors in both techniques, we can address

Fig. 8. Graph of output voltage for a) EX and b) CM PVDF-BYK 1 %.

the perceived discrepancies between the results, demonstrating their consistency within the expected uncertainty range. Furthermore, the consistency between the crystallinity values obtained from DSC and XRD is in line with the findings reported in the literature, which supports the reliability of our results [26].

3.4. Tape composition by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Fig. 4 Presents the thermogravimetric curves of BYK powder, neat PVDF, and both extruded (EX) and compressed-moulded (CM) PVDF-BYK 1 % under N_2 atmosphere. The BYK material demonstrated lower thermal stability compared to the other samples, showing a first weight loss of 2.7 wt% at 240 °C and a second one of 96.2 wt% at 378.6 °C. While neat PVDF is stable until 479.4 °C when it starts degrading showing a 74.4 wt% of weight loss at 489.5 °C and a solid remain content of 25.6 wt%. From both EX and CM PVDF-BYK 1 wt% it can be clearly seen a first weight loss of 1.5 wt% at 400 °C which corresponds to the presence of BYK and a second decay of 58 wt% at 440 °C related to the degradation of PVDF. All EX and CM PVDF-BYK samples have shown a solid content of 27–29 wt%, the same residual mass was observed by DeLisio et al. [37]. The TGA results confirm that the temperature profile set on the extruder did not degrade the BYK.

3.5. Mechanical properties by tensile test

The mechanical properties of stretched extruded and compressed

films were characterized by following the Normative UNE-EN ISO 527-3:2019 (Plastics-Determination of tensile properties) by using a universal Tensile test machine (Shimadzu with a load cell of 5 kN) The samples' dimensions (Fig. 5.) were 150 ± 5 mm in length, width between 10 and 25 ± 5 mm, thickness ≤ 1 mm and the distance between clamps was 100 ± 5 mm. The tensile tests were performed at room temperature, at a speed rate of 0.5 mm/min until a deformation of 2 % and 5 mm/min (above 2 %) until the fracture of the sample.

A uniaxial strain gauge (KFGS-5-120-C1-11 with a gauge factor of 2.11 ± 1.0 %, length of 5 mm, resistance of $119.6 \Omega \pm 0.4$ %, max. Elongation 5 %) was bonded on the central part of each sample to measure the strain and determine the associated stress. When an external tensile force is applied to the sample, the resistance of the gauge proportionally increases. The original resistance R changes by ΔR with the strain (ϵ) by following the next equation in which K_s is the gauge factor, expressing the sensitivity of the strain gauge.

$$\Delta R / R = K_s \epsilon \quad (4)$$

The electrical resistance measured by the strain gauge was recorded with a data acquisition system (HBM QuantumX MX1615B/MX1616B) by connecting the strain gauge to the acquisition system with 2 wires, in a quarter bridge configuration (DC). The Young's modulus is calculated within the strain range of 0.05 and 0.25 % in agreement with the normative.

The mechanical properties (Tensile strength, Elongation at break, Young's modulus) can be observed in Table 5. Stretched CM samples have a higher elongation at break than the EX samples but lower Young's modulus. The greater elongation at break observed in the CM samples may be attributed to their higher thickness, which inherently provides a larger cross-sectional area under stress. This expanded array of polymer chains potentially allows for enhanced slippage between them when subjected to tensile stress. Consequently, this facilitates more extensive deformation prior to the point of failure, as there is a greater capacity for the chains to disentangle and extend without being constrained by densely packed neighbouring chains [38]. As a result, the tensile strength increased due to the molecular chain's enhanced resistance to tensile forces [17]. The elongation at break for the CM samples falls within the same range as the values reported in the PVDF Kynar 720 technical data sheet, at 50 %, although the tensile strength exceeds 44–55 MPa.

Regarding the Young's modulus, which quantifies the relationship between the tensile stress (calculated, force per unit area) and axial strain (measured by the strain gauge) in the linear elastic region, the EX samples containing BYK demonstrate an elevated Young's modulus respect to CM samples, implying an increase in the stiffness. This result agrees with the β -phase content of EX samples (higher than CM strips and confirmed by FTIR results) and orientation of dipoles resulting from the applied drawing conditions such as strain rate, stretching ratio and temperature, as previously reported [16,19,39–41].

In this sense, the extruded PVDF samples containing BYK showed an average Young's modulus (3.31 GPa) higher than the bare extruded PVDF samples (2.69 GPa), suggesting that the BYK was favourable to the chain alignment and reorientation to form β -crystallites. In the same manner, enhanced tensile strength values were observed for extruded PVDF-BYK 1 % samples (230.38 MPa vs 188.96 MPa for bare extruded PVDF) The significance of the chain alignment was reported by Ferreira et al. [8], noting that the enhancement of Young's modulus is linked to an increase in the stretch ratio during the drawing process.

On the contrary, for compressed moulded samples, the addition of BYK does not show a significant improvement, while bare CM PVDF samples show slightly better mechanical properties (Young's modulus and tensile strength) but still lower than extruded samples. This can also be attributed to the drawing conditions applied since at higher stretching temperatures, the transformation of alpha to β phase is less efficient because of the mobility of molecular chains, as reported by Sajkiewicz et al. [42]. Besides, this, Mohammdi and colleagues [43] also

Fig. 9. Experimental setup for evaluating piezoelectric response tapes in a cantilever configuration under vibrational excitation. a) Measurement of output voltage using the oscilloscope; b) schematic representation of the vibrational excitation source; c) output voltage (peak-to-peak) of six individual tapes; d) physical arrangement of the tapes mounted on the vibrational source.

observed an enhancement of β -phase crystallites at a higher stretch ratio and stretching rate (as in the case of stretched extruded samples). The error observed for the maximum force and tensile strength are related to the different width of both extruded and compressed-moulded samples.

Fig. 6 Shows the stress vs strain curves of stretched and Extruded (EX) and compressed-moulded (CM) for PVDF and PVDF-BYK 1 % (five samples tested). From the strain-stress curves, the linear elastic region and a strain hardening region can clearly be observed until the sample reaches the maximum elongation, which leads to its fracture.

3.6. Piezoelectric performance of composite evaluation of d_{33} coefficient and mechanical stretching

The selected PVDF samples for evaluating piezoelectric performance were the compressed-moulded and extruded samples (both stretched) with 1 % BYK because of their high β phase content and stability during polarisation (without any electrical discharge occurring). The piezoelectric effect demonstrated by EX PVDF-BYK 1 % and CM PVDF-BYK 1 % was evaluated by the piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} , which reflects the

piezoelectric strain constant along the direction of the applied electric field (through the sample thickness) directly linked to the polarisation conditions.

The d_{33} reported in the literature for homopolymer PVDF is typically lower than 40 pC/N, however, the studies mention PVDF films typically prepared using the solvent casting method, which is known for promoting β -phase crystallization [7,13]. As shown in Fig. 7, the polarisation method was found to be coherent since it is a feature of the dipole orientation.

With a d_{33} of 25–30 pC/N, the dipoles of EX PVDF-BYK 1 % were effectively aligned in the electrical field direction. In contrast, CM PVDF-BYK 1 % exhibited a lower d_{33} value due to its reduced β -phase content, and fewer dipoles available for alignment. Additionally, the d_{33} values for CM PVDF-BYK 1 % agree with the finding of Mrlik et al. [19], who reported a value of 8–10 pC/N.

Afterwards, each tape was mechanically stimulated by a Universal tensile test machine (Shimadzu AGX-V). Regarding the d_{33} meaningful, the tensile test configuration was suitable to investigate the conversion of mechanical energy to electrical energy. Therefore, the sample was cyclically stretched from 0 N to 40 N and then force was released to 0 N before being stretched again to 40 N at a speed rate of 300 mm/min to induce bending, whereas an oscilloscope recorded the output voltage. It is noteworthy that the 40 N applied during the test falls within the elastic region, as observed by the mechanical testing.

Fig. 8 Shows the output voltage of the stretched EX PVDF-BYK 1 wt %: out of 8 tapes tested, 5 fell within the 95 % confidence interval, suggesting that the variation in the output is consistent with random sampling variability.

The same output voltage tests were conducted for the stretched CM PVDF-BYK 1 % samples, observing that most samples show an output voltage response between 7 and 12 V (showing a lower piezoelectric response than stretched EX PVDF-BYK 1 %). The difference between the output voltages obtained could be related to the different samples' thickness and polarisation effectiveness. Thinner films subjected to the same poling conditions (voltage applied and time) are more responsive, and the higher the electrical poling voltage can withstand, the bigger the output voltage response is.

3.7. Piezoelectric response of vibrating cantilever beam

A piezoelectric cantilever beam has been chosen for this study due to its high sensitivity to mechanical vibrations and its ability to efficiently convert mechanical energy into electrical energy through the piezoelectric effect. This configuration is particularly effective for energy harvesting under low-frequency vibrations, making it well-suited for applications in structural health monitoring [44].

The experimental setup, Fig. 9 a) and b), features piezoelectric tapes arranged on a cantilever beam, with one end fixed and the other end free to oscillate under controlled vibrational excitation. A vibrating shaker, driven by an amplified excitation signal, provides stimulation at an operating frequency of 14 Hz. An accelerometer connected to an Arduino microcontroller is attached to the sample to measure the system's dynamic response, as shown in Fig. 9 b). As shown in Fig. 9 c) and d), the peak-to-peak voltage of each tape averaged around 12 V at 14 Hz, which is the resonance frequency of the cantilever. This result confirms the effectiveness of the β -phase enhancement and polarisation, demonstrating reproducible results.

4. Conclusions

This work explored two fabrication methods for developing flexible piezoelectric PVDF and PVDF-BYK 1 % tapes: flat-die extrusion (EX) and compression moulding (CM) with a subsequent drawing process. The addition of BYK facilitated crystallization, further supporting the formation of the β -phase. The drawing process aimed at improving the β -phase revealed that using a temperature of 80 °C and a stretching

speed of 300 mm/min was more effective than solely considering the stretch ratio. This effectiveness was evident from the higher content of the β -phase in the EX-samples compared to the CM-samples confirmed by FTIR and XRD. The excellent piezoelectric performance, resulting from a high amount of β -phase and stability during polarisation, was demonstrated by EX PVDF-BYK 1 %, with a d_{33} value of 25–30 pC/N and a peak-to-peak voltage of 27–35 V when subjected to press-release forces. Moreover, when integrated into a cantilever beam and subjected to vibrating excitation, these samples generated a peak-to-peak voltage averaging around 12 V at 14 Hz, confirming the robustness and reproducibility of the fabrication process, the β -phase enhancement and polarisation effectiveness. These findings underscore the potential of extruded and stretched PVDF-BYK 1 % for advanced applications as energy harvesting cantilever devices, particularly where flexibility, durability, and environmentally friendly processing are required.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Amanda Melo: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David Esteves:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ignacio Ezpeleta:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Cintia Mateo-Mateo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nelson Durães:** Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: The authors declare no additional relationships or activities that may be perceived as a conflict of interest. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the European Project “InComEss” under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, grant number 862597.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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